

Appendix D: Atlas of *Gaia*-ESO SB3

In this section, we show the CCFs and the associated spectrum at all epochs for each of the detected SB3. In each figure, the left panel shows the *NACRE* (coloured lines) and *Gaia*-ESO (dashed black line) CCFs, while the right panel shows the corresponding spectrum (zoomed on the flux range [0.45, 1.1] and with the setup's full wavelength range displayed over three sub-panels). The displayed x - and y -ranges are the same for each kind of plot (CCF or spectra), such that the reader can compare directly two epochs. All the CCFs (*NACRE* or *Gaia*-ESO) are normalised such that the highest peak has its maximum at 1. The legend box reminds the CNAME of the system, the setup and the elapsed time Δ MJD since the first available epoch. The caption indicates the CNAME, epoch (MJD) and GIRAFFE setup, plus a numbering to ease the reading of the time-series. The CCFs are ordered by ascending MJD. According to the stellar waltz occurring in the examined system, one can follow the motion of the different stellar components along time: depending on the orbital phase, one can see one, two or three components.

D.1. 00195847-5423227

Fig. D.1: (1/4) CNAME 00195847-5423227, at MJD = 56532.286507, setup HR10.

Fig. D.2: (2/4) CNAME 00195847-5423227, at MJD = 56532.307888, setup HR10.

Fig. D.3: (3/4) CNAME 00195847-5423227, at MJD = 56532.362038, setup HR21.

Fig. D.4: (4/4) CNAME 00195847-5423227, at MJD = 56532.380019, setup HR21.

D.2. 08202324-1402560

Fig. D.5: (1/4) CNAME 08202324-1402560, at MJD = 56757.013357, setup HR21.

Fig. D.6: (2/4) CNAME 08202324-1402560, at MJD = 56757.031351, setup HR21.

Fig. D.7: (3/4) CNAME 08202324-1402560, at MJD = 56758.012499, setup HR10.

Fig. D.8: (4/4) CNAME 08202324-1402560, at MJD = 56758.033832, setup HR10.

D.3. 08393088-0033389

For CNAME 08393088-0033389 shown in this Section, our SB3 classification is based on Fig. D.9 and D.10. The three peaks visible on these figures stand clearly out of the correlation noise and are therefore interpreted as three potential stellar components. These secondary peaks are no longer visible in Fig. D.11 and D.12, but these spectra were acquired about 1508 hours after the first two (Fig. D.9 and D.10). The last two exposures (Fig. D.13 and D.14) are recorded about 1530 hours after the first two (Fig. D.9 and D.10) and now reveal four secondary peaks! It is unlikely that they are due to correlation noise, since peaks due to correlation noise should appear the same at all epochs whereas the peaks of Fig. D.11 and D.12 are clean. Clearly this system deserves a follow-up to elucidate its exact nature (SB3 or even **maybe a SB5**); it illustrates how complex it can be to characterise high-multiplicity systems.

Fig. D.9: (1/6) CNAME 08393088-0033389, at MJD = 56314.185014, setup HR10.

Fig. D.10: (2/6) CNAME 08393088-0033389, at MJD = 56314.205499, setup HR10.

Fig. D.11: (3/6) CNAME 08393088-0033389, at MJD = 56377.008829, setup HR10.

Fig. D.12: (4/6) CNAME 08393088-0033389, at MJD = 56377.029952, setup HR10.

Fig. D.13: (5/6) CNAME 08393088-0033389, at MJD = 56378.014598, setup HR21.

Fig. D.14: (6/6) CNAME 08393088-0033389, at MJD = 56378.032579, setup HR21.

D.4. 08402079-0025437

For CNAME 08402079-0025437 shown in this Section, our SB3 classification is based on Fig. D.15, D.16, D.19 and D.20. From Figures D.15 and D.16, we are confident in the existence of at least two stellar components. We may exclude the doubling as due to a shock from the variations occurring at later times, the CCF becoming either cleaner (single-peaked on Fig. D.17 and D.18) or more complex (multiply peaked on Fig. D.19 and D.20, which is not at all expected for pulsating variables). The third peak on Fig. D.15 and D.16 is admittedly just above the noise level. But from Fig. D.19 and D.20, we interpret the three peaks with a height larger than or equal to 0.5 to be tracers of the stellar components. One might wonder, as for the previous system, whether the system might not even be of higher multiplicity, as judged by the peak with a height of 0.3. As for the previous system, a dedicated spectroscopic follow-up is needed to assess the SB n nature of 08402079-0025437.

Fig. D.15: (1/6) CNAME 08402079-0025437, at MJD = 56314.185014, setup HR10.

Fig. D.16: (2/6) CNAME 08402079-0025437, at MJD = 56314.205499, setup HR10.

Fig. D.17: (3/6) CNAME 08402079-0025437, at MJD = 56377.008829, setup HR10.

Fig. D.18: (4/6) CNAME 08402079-0025437, at MJD = 56377.029952, setup HR10.

Fig. D.19: (5/6) CNAME 08402079-0025437, at MJD = 56378.014598, setup HR21.

Fig. D.20: (6/6) CNAME 08402079-0025437, at MJD = 56378.032579, setup HR21.

D.5. 15120307-4049481

Fig. D.21: (1/4) CNAME 15120307-4049481, at MJD = 56445.093053, setup HR10.

Fig. D.22: (2/4) CNAME 15120307-4049481, at MJD = 56445.114255, setup HR10.

Fig. D.23: (3/4) CNAME 15120307-4049481, at MJD = 56446.197221, setup HR21.

Fig. D.24: (4/4) CNAME 15120307-4049481, at MJD = 56446.215217, setup HR21.

D.6. 15161563-4125518

Fig. D.25: (1/4) CNAME 15161563-4125518, at MJD = 56443.110397, setup HR10.

Fig. D.26: (2/4) CNAME 15161563-4125518, at MJD = 56443.131571, setup HR10.

Fig. D.27: (3/4) CNAME 15161563-4125518, at MJD = 56444.196398, setup HR21.

Fig. D.28: (4/4) CNAME 15161563-4125518, at MJD = 56444.214383, setup HR21.

D.7. 15420717-4407146

Fig. D.29: (1/4) CNAME 15420717-4407146, at MJD = 56377.359329, setup HR10.

Fig. D.30: (2/4) CNAME 15420717-4407146, at MJD = 56377.380557, setup HR10.

Fig. D.31: (3/4) CNAME 15420717-4407146, at MJD = 56378.340677, setup HR21.

Fig. D.32: (4/4) CNAME 15420717-4407146, at MJD = 56378.358684, setup HR21.

D.8. 16003634-0745523

Fig. D.33: (1/4) CNAME 16003634-0745523, at MJD = 56798.161286, setup HR10.

Fig. D.34: (2/4) CNAME 16003634-0745523, at MJD = 56798.182565, setup HR10.

Fig. D.35: (3/4) CNAME 16003634-0745523, at MJD = 56798.252817, setup HR21.

Fig. D.36: (4/4) CNAME 16003634-0745523, at MJD = 56798.270793, setup HR21.

D.9. 18170244-4227076

Fig. D.37: (1/4) CNAME 18170244-4227076, at MJD = 56821.258156, setup HR10.

Fig. D.38: (2/4) CNAME 18170244-4227076, at MJD = 56821.279464, setup HR10.

Fig. D.39: (3/4) CNAME 18170244-4227076, at MJD = 57180.349352, setup HR21.

Fig. D.40: (4/4) CNAME 18170244-4227076, at MJD = 57180.367370, setup HR21.

D.10. 21393685-4659598

Fig. D.41: (1/4) CNAME 21393685-4659598, at MJD = 57265.128815, setup HR21.

Fig. D.42: (2/4) CNAME 21393685-4659598, at MJD = 57265.146791, setup HR21.

Fig. D.43: (3/4) CNAME 21393685-4659598, at MJD = 57265.217895, setup HR10.

Fig. D.44: (4/4) CNAME 21393685-4659598, at MJD = 57265.239211, setup HR10.

Appendix E: Atlas of *Gaia*-ESO SB4

In this section, we show the CCFs and the associated spectrum at all epochs for each of the detected SB4. In each figure, the left panel shows the N_{ACRE} (coloured lines) and *Gaia*-ESO (dashed black line) CCFs, while the right panel shows the corresponding spectrum (zoomed on the flux range [0.45, 1.1] and with the setup's full wavelength range displayed over three sub-panels). The displayed x - and y -ranges are the same for each kind of plot (CCF or spectra), such that the reader can compare directly two epochs. All the CCFs (N_{ACRE} or *Gaia*-ESO) are normalised such that the highest peak has its maximum at 1. The legend box reminds the CNAME of the system, the setup and the elapsed time ΔMJD since the first available epoch. The caption indicates the CNAME, epoch (MJD) and GIRAFFE setup, plus a numbering to ease the reading of the time-series. The CCFs are ordered by ascending MJD. According to the stellar waltz occurring in the examined system, one can follow the motion of the different stellar components along time: depending on the orbital phase, one can see one, two, three or four components. These systems are highly likely at least SB3, while the existence of a fourth component is only tentative: for this reason, we briefly comment at the beginning of each section the interpretation of the CCFs pointing at an SB4.

E.1. 18263326-3146508

Figure E.1 shows two stellar components whose velocities are around 120 km s^{-1} and 180 km s^{-1} . Figure E.2 shows a third stellar component whose velocity is between the first two stellar components. A fourth tentative stellar component might exist at $v_{\text{rad}} \approx 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. This local maximum exists at the two available epochs and in all CCFs, decreasing the probability for it to be correlation noise.

Fig. E.1: (1/2) CNAME 18263326-3146508, at MJD = 56857.033274, setup HR21.

Fig. E.2: (2/2) CNAME 18263326-3146508, at MJD = 56857.065142, setup HR21.

E.2. 19243943+0048136

Figures E.3 and E.4 show four stellar components whose velocities are between $\approx -100 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ and $\approx 180 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. We note that they are all within the main peak of the very wide *Gaia*-ESO CCF; an inflexion point can be seen in the *Gaia*-ESO CCF where the component with the largest velocity lies. The local maximum at $v \approx 200 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ might be correlation noise since if it was a genuine stellar component, we would expect to see at least an inflexion point in the *Gaia*-ESO CCF at this velocity (*Gaia*-ESO CCF are less prone to correlation noise thanks to their correlating masks). Figures E.9 and E.10 might show only three components: the local maximum at $v \approx 150 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ might be correlation noise. The other epochs plotted here show either one, two or three stellar components.

Fig. E.3: (1/12) CNAME 19243943+0048136, at MJD = 56074.421068, setup HR21.

Fig. E.4: (2/12) CNAME 19243943+0048136, at MJD = 56074.431550, setup HR21.

Fig. E.5: (3/12) CNAME 19243943+0048136, at MJD = 56099.378781, setup HR10.

Fig. E.6: (4/12) CNAME 19243943+0048136, at MJD = 56099.391848, setup HR10.

Fig. E.7: (5/12) CNAME 19243943+0048136, at MJD = 56171.003662, setup HR10.

Fig. E.8: (6/12) CNAME 19243943+0048136, at MJD = 56171.017543, setup HR10.

Fig. E.9: (7/12) CNAME 19243943+0048136, at MJD = 56171.078342, setup HR21.

Fig. E.10: (8/12) CNAME 19243943+0048136, at MJD = 56171.088809, setup HR21.

Fig. E.11: (9/12) CNAME 19243943+0048136, at MJD = 56197.977533, setup HR10.

Fig. E.12: (10/12) CNAME 19243943+0048136, at MJD = 56198.001631, setup HR10.

Fig. E.13: (11/12) CNAME 19243943+0048136, at MJD = 56204.014924, setup HR10.

Fig. E.14: (12/12) CNAME 19243943+0048136, at MJD = 56204.028780, setup HR10.

